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The Portuguese tile in the Rudmin Acculturation Learning Model: A fusion case

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ABSTRACT

The article is applying the Rudmin Model (2009) into the Portuguese context of acculturation. It states that the Portuguese context is working in a fusion way. The fusion acculturation feature is visible in the Portuguese tile and in the "French house". The acculturative learning process is changing according to the social status of who is borrowing and mixing stranger cultural features into the Portuguese culture.

Keywords: Rudmin Model, fusion acculturation, emigration, imitation.

1. An attempt to define acculturation

This article aims to display the importance of the material acculturation for the acculturation topic. The article main goals are; to shed light on the Portuguese culture of acculturation, taking into account the Rudmin Model (2009). And, to apply the Rudmin Model on the material acculturation topic, displaying how the appraisals about the own cultural changes are changing according to the social status.

The word acculturation was coined by Powell: "The force of acculturation under the overwhelming presence of millions of civilized people has brought great changes." (Powell, 1880, p. 46). Powell conceived the acculturation phenomenon as a two-way process,

because the linguistic exchange occurred among the American native tribes, and still among the Europeans and the native tribes (Powell, 1891).

In the current article the acculturation phenomenon is defined as a second culture acquisition (Powell, 1880, 1891; Rudmin, 2009) at individual (Graves, 1967) and at collective levels (Boas, 1982; Herskovits, & Herskovits, 1934; Malinowski, 1958). Acculturation results from the mutual cultural transmission due to the intercultural contact among different cultures (Redfield, Linton, & Herskovits, 1936). Acculturation is a universal, multidimensional, and it is a dynamic process of cultural transmission among cultures. Acculturation is always under construction, and it is inner to cultural diversity, because the cultural exchanges among the different cultures are doing new cultural structures (Berry, 2008), new cultural borders, and new ethnic identities (Barth, 1969). The reciprocal cultural exchanges can occur under conflictual, problematic, and under consensual relationships (Bastide, 1971; Bourhis, Moise, Perreault, & Senécal, 1997; Devereux, & Loeb, 1943; Sabatier, & Boutry, 2006). Acculturation often triggers concerns about the cultural changes, and conflicts at internal, at intercultural, and at international levels.

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) have written that there are three models in order approach the acculturation phenomenon; the assimilation, the multicultural, and the fusion model. The assimilation and the multicultural models are very well-known. The fusion model can be defined as a mixture between two cultures (Arends-Tóth, & Van de Vijver, 2006), ending in a new culture (Coleman, 1995; Kagitçibaşın, 2007). According to LaFromboise, Coleman and Gerton (1993), the fusion model does not suppose the perception of a cultural superiority from the ruler cultural group, regarding the “minority” culture, and the cultural exchange is running in all directions.

Some prominent scholars as Herskovits (Leal, 2011), Linton (1937) and Spicer (1954) approached acculturation employing a fusion point of view. In the Portuguese or in the Lusophone cultural contexts, important authors as Freyre (1986), Holanda (1948) and Bastide (1971) have done the same. Freyre conceptualized the Luso-Tropical consensus

ideology (Almeida, 2004; Vala, Lopes, & Lima, 2008), saying that the Portuguese people were more prone to mix people and cultures than most part of the European cultures, mainly more than the Anglo-Saxon culture. And, indeed, in the United States of America, the percentages of intermarriage the among different ethnic groups are low (Qian, & Lichter, 2007). However, in the Portuguese acculturative context, the biological mixtures were usual, as it is visible in Brazil (Freyre, 1986) or Cape Verde.

2. The Rudmin Model

(Figure number 1, Source: Adapted from Arends-Tóth, & Van de Vijver, 2006)

According to the figure number one, in the acculturation topic the psychological research has three components; the conditions, the cultural attitudes, and their outcomes (Arends-Tóth, & Van de Vijver, 2006). The conditions or the antecedents are the variables which can shape the acculturation process. In the assimilation model conditions, as the upward social mobility or the difference among generations, are typical variables (Scott, 2009). In the Berry Model (2001, 2007) the cultural attitudes are mediating the outcomes in the ethnic identity, or in the health topics, and the conditions are not taken into account.

(Figure number 2, Source: Adapted from Rudmin, 2009)

As it is visible in the figure number two, in the Rudmin Model (2009) acculturation appears as a three-stage process with covariation through low socioeconomic status (SES), and discrimination. The main acculturation topics (Ward, 2004) are present in the model; the cultural attitudes, the ethnic identity, the coping model, and it was added the utility decision. All of them are treated as antecedents or as conditions, because they are influencing the learning process. The main difference between the Rudmin Model and the pervasive Berry Model is that in the former the learning process appears as a mediator, and not as an outcome (Arends-Tóth, & Van de Vijver, 2006), and that the low SES and discrimination are controlling the acculturation process. Therefore, learning is occupying the place that was ascribed for the cultural attitudes, and the attitudes are treated as conditions.

3. The Portuguese tile and the "French House"

Manuel I (1469-1521), a Portuguese king, travelled to Seville, Spain. He came back to Portugal delighted with the Al-Andalus tile. Afterward, he decorated a Portuguese palace with Spanish tiles, which had Islamic roots. Since that time, the tile became typical into the Portuguese culture.

In the Manuel I intercultural experience is possible to find out different ways to learn a second culture. Firstly, the king curiosity about the tiles. Secondly, it is also possible to find out to get information about the tiles, because the king devised diligences to get more knowledge about the tiles. Afterward, it is possible to find out mentoring because he promoted the tiles craft and its industry in Portugal. And it is also possible to find out instruction, because the king Manuel I promoted it. However, imitation is the main way to learn a second culture, and to mix cultural influences into new ones. Imitation (Bandura, 1965) works due to the social models, and due to the behaviors, which are displaying an adaptive capacity. According to Spicer (1954), in the 17th century, under a “peaceful” intercultural relationship, the Yaqui people had accepted the Jesuits, because they obtained advantages in their culture, for instance, benefits in the agriculture production. Therefore, the Jesuits obtained social influence, and they acted as social models for the Yaquis. The Jesuits also adapted cultural features from the Yaqui culture, doing a two-way process of

acculturation. The king Manuel I imitated the Moorish Spanish tiles, because of their beautiful features, and also because the tiles were useful.

The king Manuel I brief story about the tile is useful to shed light on the acculturation phenomenon. The Portuguese tile is a case of material acculturation, although the tile can display how the Portuguese or the Brazilian cultures are shaped by an acculturative fusion culture. During the Age of Discovery, the tiles were transported to other Lusophones countries, and to other cultures. Therefore, the Portuguese tile displays a fusion acculturation shape, blending different cultural features.

A different example of the material and the fusion acculturation is displayed by the Portuguese emigrants, in France, because of their low social status. In France, during the 60s, most of the Portuguese immigrants were males working in the construction sector. They learnt to build the "French house" in their workplaces. Afterward, the French style was transported and imitated into Portugal. However, in the Portuguese culture, the appraisal about the "French house" was negative (Castro, 2011; Castro & Marques, 2003; Villanova, 2006), in spite that it represented an improvement in the living conditions (Villanova, 2006).

Thereby, the imitation of the tile encompassed a positive social status; it was done by a successful king. However, the "French house" was done by emigrants, and consequently by people with a low social status, and provoked concerns about the Portuguese cultural changes. The difference between the tile, and the "French house" is placed in the social status of who was borrowing them.

4. The concerns with the cultural changes and conclusions

The difference between with the positive or the negative appraisals about the material acculturation by imitation seems to underlie in the social status. The emigrant's low social status became them not trustful social models. The concern with the cultural changes seems to be universal. In the "French house" case, the concern with the own cultural changes

occurs inside the same culture, thus, in the Portuguese one. However, often the concerns about the cultural changes are appearing regarding different cultures. Thereby, the appraisal about the cultural changes can render to international conflicts.

The question about how to do intercultural relationships and to change our own culture, and the different cultures remains unsolved through the acculturation models; the assimilation, the multicultural, and the fusion one. However, the Portuguese tile and the "French house" are displaying that is possible to go beyond the overreaction about our own cultural changes. New mixtures are resulting in new types of cultures, leading to new cultural exchanges, and to cultural diversity. Thereby, the material acculturation has the potentially to display that another World based on the mutual learning and in the diversity is not only possible, but rather that it is in front of our eyes into our shared material culture.

Linton, in 1937, wrote about an American man who was awaking concerned with the cultural changes in the North American culture. The American citizen did not notice that everything around him, and everything that he was using in that morning was done throughout the World History by different cultures, and civilizations at material and at symbolic levels:

There can be no question about the average American's Americanism or his desire to preserve this precious heritage at all costs . . . he will not fail to thank a Hebrew God in an Indo-European language that he is a one hundred percent (decimal system invented by the Greeks) American (from Americus Vespucci, Italian geographer.). (Linton, 1937, pp. 427-429)

Linton reminds us that the material is interconnected with the symbolic culture, and that the fears about the own cultural changes often can be an overreaction.

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